

TRACING THE JOURNEY OF QUIET QUITTING THROUGH BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Purpose: The primary objective of the present study is to trace the journey of research in quiet quitting through bibliometric analysis and to have a deep-dive into top 30 cited documents in the domain.

Design/methodology/approach: For undertaking the bibliometric analysis, SCOPUS-based journals published till 26 January 2025 were explored using the keywords "quiet quitting" OR "silent resignation". Out of 115 documents, 82 were finally processed using the VOSVIEWER software.

Findings: It was found that quiet quitting has gained attention recently, particularly after great resignations in the year 2022. The United States has published the maximum papers, followed by Greece and India. However, in terms of citations, Greece is at the top, followed by Italy and United States. Document-wise majority of papers have been published in the domain of business and management. Top five cited documents include Formica (2022), Hamouche (2023), Serenko (2024), Boy (2023) and Galanis (2023). Top five keywords used in the domain are burnout, professional burnout, employee disengagement, healthcare personnel, healthcare workers. It is recommended that in context of quitting, there is a need to conduct study on impact of organisational communication, including poor, internal, manipulative, ineffective and negative communication, miscommunication, darkside and loyalty on quiet quitting.

Originality: The paper is original contribution of authors.

Research limitations/implications: The bibliometric analysis is limited to the documents published in the Scopus journals only. No other database has been explored.

Practical implications: The present study recommends the areas which are not yet explored or are less explored which, if researched in future, will add value to the existing literature.

Keywords: Quiet Quitting, Bibliometric Analysis, Vosviewer, Silent Resignation, Employee Withdrawal, Employee Disengagement

Introduction

In the last few years, the idea of quiet quitting (QQ) has gained significant attention as a prolific trend in the labour market, particularly in the post-pandemic era (Zhang, 2022; Formica and Sfodera, 2022). According to Marks (2023), "Quiet Quitting" was coined by Mark Boldger, an economist in the year 2008 to express attitude shift of the workforce. This phenomenon involves employees disengaging emotionally from their work while continuing to fulfil their core responsibilities, effectively doing the bare minimum required to maintain their employment (Hinkley and Taylor, 2022). Quiet quitters are disengaged workers who have no intention of going beyond or above their prescribed work. The basic premise of QQ is a clear existence of work-life boundaries, with the employee satisfying the minimum requirements of the job, prioritising their wellbeing (Taper, 2022; Marks, 2023). Quiet quitting is often characterised by a lack of enthusiasm, reduced participation in non-essential tasks, a low investment in work-related activities, and a focus on maintaining a healthier work-life balance (Kim, 2022). Formica and Sfodera (2022) define QQ as the limited commitment of employees to perform the assigned duties and to relinquish any other task not specified in their job description. According to Hamouche et al (2023), it is similar to collective industrial action such as "work to rule" and "acting one's wage," as well as work withdrawal, employee cynicism, and silence. Serenko (2024) defined quiet quitting as "a mindset in which employees deliberately limit work activities to their job description, meet yet not exceed the pre-established expectations, never volunteer for additional tasks and do all this to merely maintain their current employment status while prioritizing their well-being over organizational goals." Multiple theories and concepts are used to lay the foundation for understanding the conceptualization and operationalization of quiet quitting (e.g. organizational citizenship behaviour, social exchange, psychological contract, organizational justice, conflict theory, equity theory, two-factor theory, job demands-resources and conservation of resources theories (Hamouche et al., 2023). The trend, initially associated with Generation Z, has spread across various age groups, reflecting broader issues such as burnout, unfulfilled expectations, and changing personal priorities (Gallup, 2022). As a result, organizations face challenges in managing employee engagement and productivity, necessitating a better comprehension of the fundamental reasons and

effects of quiet quitting (Bakker and Demerouti, 2017).

Quiet quitting (QQ) is often more than just an individual choice; it's usually driven by underlying issues in the workplace. Factors like financial stress, poor health, pay inequality, work-life imbalance, lack of recognition, and the absence of growth opportunities can all contribute to QQ (Nimmi et al., 2024). Dutta et al. (2024) found that workplace ostracism significantly motivates employees to withdraw. Additionally, Bansal and Garg (2024) discovered that conflicts at work—whether related to tasks or relationships—are a major cause of quiet quitting in the Indian IT sector. QQ has also been linked to negative workplace gossip (Srivastava et al., 2024). Understanding these root causes is crucial for organizations to address the issues and create a healthier work environment. The consequences of quiet quitting can be severe. It often leads to reduced cognitive engagement, lower participation in team discussions, and a decline in knowledge-sharing activities, which can undermine the overall learning culture of an organization (Srivastava et al., 2024). Quiet quitting can also stifle innovation and creativity, further impacting the company's growth (Ustun et al., 2024). Research has shown that it can diminish work efficiency, weaken commitment towards the organization, and damage the company's culture (Papadopoulou and Vouzis, 2024). Moreover, during the times of digital transformation, quiet quitting has been found to lower job satisfaction and commitment, increasing the likelihood of employees leaving their jobs (Kim and Lee, 2024). Given these impacts, it's clear that understanding and addressing quiet quitting is extremely important for organizations to nurture a more involved and effective workforce. However, some researchers challenge the conventional negative view of quiet quitting. For example, Tsemach and Barth (2023) studied 1,179 Israeli teachers and found that quiet quitting could be positive and can help to reduce burnout. Dillard et al. (2024) also looked at quiet quitting from a more individualistic perspective, concluding that it can have benefits not just for the individual, but also for organizations and society as a whole. These findings suggest that quiet quitting might have positive aspects that deserve further exploration. Ultimately, studying quiet quitting is important not only to better understand human and organizational behaviour, but also to tackle the challenges it presents.

This bibliometric analysis endeavours to explore the existing literature on quiet quitting, examining its definitions, causes, and impacts on employees

and organizations. By analysing the current research landscape, this study seeks to meet the following objectives:

Objectives

- (1) To identify the trends, top cited documents, top authors in literature on quiet quitting.
- (2) To trace the journey of research in quiet quitting through keyword analysis.

- (3) To analyse the focus of top 30 papers in the domain of quiet quitting.

Methodology

115 documents were found in *SCOPUS-based journals* using the keywords "quiet quitting" OR "silent resignation" on 26 January 2025. 82 were finally processed for further analysis. The current research has made use of *VOSVIEWER software* for bibliometric analysis.

Table I Acceptance and Rejection Criteria

Criteria	Acceptance	Rejection
Document Type	Articles (81) Conference Papers (8)	Book chapter (8) Review (5) Editorial (5) Note (3) Conference review (3) Book (2)
Language	English (112)	German (1) Greek (1) Hungarian (1)
Source Type	Journal (94) Conference Proceedings (5)	Book (9) Book series (7)
Relevance	Relevant (83)	Irrelevant (1)

Analysis and Findings

Figure I: Documents published year-wise

The figure-I shows that the papers are published starting in 2022 and majority of them are published in the year 2024. Hence, it is concluded that the research in the domain of quiet quitting is of recent interest to academicians.

Figure-II Country-wise publications and Network

The figure-II and table -II shows that the United States (16.5%) published the majority of the papers related to quiet quitting, followed by Greece (9.7%), India (7.7%), Turkey (6.7%), Malaysia (4.8%), the United Arab Emirates (4.8%), and the United Kingdom (4.8%). All these countries have produced at least five papers. Quiet Quitting got initial attraction in United Kingdom, Poland, Malaysia and Philippines. Later in United States took it up and in countries including India, France, Russian Federation, it is of recent origin.

Table II Country-wise Number of Documents Published

Countries	Publications
United States	17
Greece	10
India	8
Turkey	7
Malaysia, United Arab Emirates, United Kingdom	5 each
Australia, France, Indonesia, Italy,	4 each
Canada, South Korea	3 each
Philippines, Poland, Portugal, Spain	2 each
Austria, China, Cyprus, Dominican Republic, Germany, Hungary, Israel, Lebanon, North Macedoni, Russian Federation, Saudi Arabia, Singapore, Thailand, Vietnam, Undefined	1 each

Table-III and figure -III presents the list of top cited papers alongwith their link strength. As per the data top cited documents are by Formica (2022) followed by Hamouche (2023) and Serenko (2024).

Table III Top Cited Documents

Sr. No.	Document	Citations	Links
1	Formica (2022)	104	31
2	Hamouche (2023)	48	22
3	Serenko (2024)	48	10
4	Boy (2023)	29	0
5	Galanis (2023)	23	16
6	Anand (2025)	21	4

7	Lu (2023)	19	1
8	Moon (2023)	18	0
9	Galanis (2024b)	14	3
10	Zuzelo (2023)	14	7
11	Xueyun (2023)	13	1
12	Galanis (2024a)	12	7
13	Liu-Lastres (2024)	11	5
14	Galanis (2024f)	11	3

Figure-III Top Cited Documents

The data on citations as presented in table-IV shows that total 82 documents were found and 82 meet the threshold of having at least one citation. All were processed and 57 were linked citations. On the basis of the results shown in table-IV the top cited authors Galanis, P., Katsiroumpa, A., Moisoglou, I. and Vraka, I. All these authors have been cited 72 times.

Table IV Top Cited Authors

Author	Documents	Citations
Galanis, Petros	8	72
Katsiroumpa, Aglaia	8	72
Moisoglou, Ioannis	8	72
Vraka, Irene	7	72
Kaitelidou, Daphne	4	60
Konstantakopoulou, Olympia	4	60
Siskou, Olga	4	60
Gallos, Parisi	6	49
Al Mamun, Abdullah	4	33
Yang, Qing	4	33
Masukujjaman, Mohammad	2	32
Anand, Amitabh	2	21
Malliarou, Maria	2	20
Papathanasiou, Ioanna V.	2	20
Xueyun, Zhong	3	14

Figure IV shows the results of co-occurrence analysis. Out of 429 keywords used in the documents under this study, 82 keywords have occurred for 2 or more than 2 times. The keywords are divided into 9 clusters. Cluster 1 comprises 18

keywords covering quiet quitting and burnout including burnout, professional burnout, employee disengagement, healthcare personnel, healthcare workers, nursing, reliability, validity, surveys and questionnaires, psychology, quiet

firing, quiet quitting scale, young adult, and middle-aged. Cluster 2 comprises 17 items covering work environment including article, conservation of resources, delivery of healthcare, employee, healthcare delivery, human, humans, inclusion, job satisfaction, nurses, psychological safety, social media, turnover intentions, work environment, working conditions, and workplace. Cluster 3 comprises of 16 items based on work-life balance including Covid 19, employee engagement, employee wellbeing, gen z, generation z, great resignation, human resource management, hustle culture, job burnout, millennials, organizational, quiet quitting, role conflict, turnover, and work-life balance. Cluster 4 consists of 16 items including adult, behaviour, coronavirus disease 2019, cross-sectional studies, cross-sectional study, epidemiology, female, male, motivation, pandemic, pandemics, physician, sars-cov-2, severe acute respiratory syndrome, united states and wellbeing. Cluster 5-6 items including conceptual framework, human capital, organization, organizational commitment, scale development, and social exchange theory. Cluster 6 includes 3 items i.e. organizational citizenship behaviour, satisfaction and, work engagement. Cluster 7 includes emotional exhaustion and workload. Further, the keyword analysis as per

figure-IV shows that the topic under the study has evolved from a focus on the pandemic and healthcare sector at the beginning of 2023 to work environment, engagement, and citizenship behaviour and ultimately burnout, work-life balance, and well-being at the end of 2023. Very recent studies focus on scale development and concepts such as social media, hustle culture, job satisfaction, and turnover intentions. The analysis of all 429 keywords shows that there are domains which carries very few studies in context with quiet quitting. For example, employee performance shows co-occurrence with keywords like employee withdrawal and erg theory. Knowledge hiding has been studied with NCA, pls predict and workplace ostracism. Cross-cultural management has co-occurrence with ethical leadership, hotel employees, inner resignation and service innovation behaviour. Human resource development has co-occurrence with humanism and multilevel analysis. Work alienation has co-occurrence with inclusive leadership and relational job design. There is no keyword with job design. However, the country India has been cited in 8 documents which are of recent origin as the average publication year is 2024. The themes of the documents published in India are shown in table-V.

Figure IV Co-occurrence Analysis

Table V: Themes of the Documents Published in India

Authors	Title	Year	Journal	Citations
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Agarwal P; Kaur; Budhwar P	Silencing Quiet Quitting: Crafting a Symphony of High-Performance Work Systems and Psychological Conditions	2024	Human Resource Management	0
Baidya M; Maity B	A strategic process to manage the right value proposition with retailers in the B2C sector	2024	Business Process Management Journal	0
Bansal S; Garg N	Quitting silently: Longitudinal research on the impact of workplace conflict and nonviolent work behavior	2024	Conflict Resolution Quarterly	2
Dutta DS; Thomas A; Shiva A; Papa A; Cuomo MT	The hustle behind knowledge: role of workplace ostracism and knowledge hiding towards quiet quitting in knowledge-intensive organisations	2024	Journal of Knowledge Management	1
Nimmi PM; Syed F; Manjaly NB; Harsha G.	Employee's narrative on quiet quitting - a qualitative analysis	2024	Employee Relations	2
Srivastava A; Pandey A; Sharma D; Ghosh K	Apathy under the surface: Theorizing quiet quitting's impact on organizational learning	2024	Development and Learning in Organizations	0
Srivastava S; Saxena A; Kapoor V; Qadir A	Sailing through silence: Exploring how negative gossip leaves breeding grounds for quiet quitting in the workplace	2024	International Journal of Conflict Management	2
Anand A; Doll J; Ray P	Drowning in silence: a scale development and validation of quiet quitting and quiet firing	2023	International Journal of Organizational Analysis	21

Discussion and Review of Top Papers

The deep dive into review of top 30 documents in the domain shows that the focus is generally on antecedents of quiet quitting and researches are more of exploratory in nature. Few papers are industry specific and few are across industry. In context of tourism industry Hamouche et al. (2023) observed that the advent of QQ can be attributed to COVID 19 changing the job market. The antecedents of QQ identified by the researchers include employees forsaking the hustle culture, searching fulfilment beyond paid work, burnout, poor management and leadership, and employee dissatisfaction and disengagement. Further, the researchers concluded that this phenomenon is more widespread in the younger generation (Gen Z). Analysing hospital industry, Formica and Sfodera (2022) identified great resignation and quiet quitting as two recent changes that have affected organisations. Due to this hospitality managers are rethinking about internal human resource and marketing strategies. The researchers explained employees' needs, values, and purpose lead to Great Resignation and Quiet Quitting. Further on antecedents Serenko (2024) analysed 672 TikTok comments, secondary data and a literature review. The results identified lack of motivation, job burnout and complaints against immediate bosses or institutions were found as the antecedents of quiet quitting. In order to address

QQ, Serenko recommends that HR managers should focus on knowledge sharing, capturing the data of expected quiet quitters, and investing in burnout management programs. The study also suggests promoting interactional justice, fairly compensating employees for extra effort, and encouraging work-life balance. Policymakers are advised to focus on preventing national human capital depletion and supporting employee mental health and efficiency innovation. Liu-Lastres et al. (2024) in a qualitative study of the hospitality and tourism industry found that quiet quitting has the following antecedents: individual factors such as demographic variables, personality of employee, involvement of industry, and issues of individuals and aspects related to work such as work-related concerns, human related concerns, work environment, and organizational concerns. The researcher also identifies work correlates with dissatisfaction w.r.t. career. job, expectations that are not met, social loafing, depleting organizational commitment, lack of career adaptivity and on-the-job embeddedness. They also concluded that QQ has effects on employees (poor job performance, work disengagement, and disengagement in pro environmental behaviours), customers (poor service quality), and business (workforce, business performance, and declines in pro-environmental behaviours). Several

suggestions to address the issue such as fit between individual and organisation, work flexibility and the well-being of employee were proposed by the researchers. Nimmi et al. (2024) explored research papers on the reasons and behavioural manifestations of the employees who quiet quit. Using exploratory qualitative approach, the researchers concluded three major reasons for QQ namely personal reasons, organizational policies and practices, and people dynamics. Bansal and Garg (2024) in their longitudinal study among IT sector employees found that work conflict (including task conflict and relationship conflict) lead to QQ. Also, practicing non-violent work behaviour reduces QQ due to work conflict. Boy and Sürmeli (2023) identified poor management, poor work-life balance, and differences in the expectations of the Z generation leading to emotional exhaustion in turn causing disengagement and depersonalization over time as the antecedents of QQ in the healthcare sector. Lu et al. (2023) in a quantitative study of 698 young Chinese lecturers proposed a conceptual model to study the effects of work overload, perceived career development opportunities, perceived pay-for-performance, influence organizational commitment and work conditions on job burnout, employee well-being, and quiet-quitting intention. Using SEM, the researchers found that all factors under study burnout and well-being of employees which in turn significantly influence QQ intentions. Additionally, psychological empowerment plays a moderating role in the effect of job burnout and employee well-being on quiet-quitting intention. Moon et al. (2023) studied the progression of employees from the stage of burnout to the voluntary resignations during and post-pandemic in the United States. The first study of 360 respondents led to the conclusion that higher extraversion in employees led to lower burnout, thus, fewer turnover rates. The second study used an additional sample of 137 to indicate that extraversion buffers the effect of role overload. Similar results were found by Xueyun et al. (2023) who surveyed 683 Chinese Gen Z employees. Marks (2023) reviewed UK government data and established that “The Great Resignation” was happening in UK. The author argued that the QQ gained popularity through social media. Wu and Wei (2024) analysed data from 563 respondents using SEM and concluded that deviant behaviour is a result of two mechanisms, namely, role ambiguity and role conflict. Few researchers also developed and validate instrument to measure quiet quitting. Anand et al. (2025) developed and validated a QQ scale and tested on 264 employees working in India. Karrani

et al. (2024) developed the QQS (Quiet Quitting Scale). Through multiphase process and rigorous testing using three samples from service organizations, the authors exhibited convergent, discriminant and criteria related validity. Galanis et al. (2023) developed and validated an instrument to measure QQ. The QQ scale was created through extensive literature review and interviews. Through EFA and CFA three factors were confirmed including detachment, lack of both initiative and motivation, with a total of nine items. Galanis et al. (2024f) analysed the data from 629 nurses in Greece collected with the “Quiet Quitting” scale. 60.9% nurses were found to be quiet quitters.

Literature also focused relationship between quiet quitting and other variables. Galanis et al. (2024), in a cross-sectional study assessed the association between *Sociodemographic variables, job burnout and job satisfaction on level of QQ*. The researchers reported that 67.4% of nurses in the selected sample were quiet quitters, while 53.8% physicians and 40.3% other HCWs were quiet quitters. Job burnout and job satisfaction contributed to QQ. Shift workers and private sector employees have more chances of QQ. In other study Galanis et al. (2024c) attempted to determine the optimal point for the Quiet Quitting Scale using Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) analysis on data from Greece. The study found that the QQS demonstrated the power to predict job satisfaction, burnout, and turnover intention. Employees scoring ≥ 2.06 were classified as quiet quitters. The authors suggest further research to confirm and validate these findings. Suhendar et al. (2023) investigated the impact of job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and organizational citizenship behavior on quiet quitting in the context of Indonesian digital start-ups. Using data from 269 employees and analysing it with PLS SEM, the study found that both job satisfaction and organizational commitment significantly influenced organizational citizenship behavior and quiet quitting. Additionally, organizational citizenship behavior was found to significantly impact QQ and mediated the relationship between OC and QQ, but it did not act as mediator between job satisfaction and quiet quitting.

Identifying relationship between emotional intelligence and quiet quitting, Galanis et al. (2024a) conducted a cross-sectional study with 992 nurses in Greece. It was concluded that there is a significant negative relationship between emotional intelligence and quiet quitting, turnover intention, and job burnout. Srivastava et al. (2024) applied the conservation of resources theory and surveyed 267 employees from varied sectors. The researchers found a

positive link between negative workplace gossip and QQ. Further, researchers identified a mediating impact of stress and emotional exhaustion in the relationship between workplace gossip and QQ. Galanis et al. (2024d) studied the effect of workplace bullying on quiet quitting with mediating effect of coping strategies. 650 nurses in Greece participated in the study. Researchers found that workplace bullying and negative coping strategies positively affect quiet quitting, while positive coping strategies negatively affect quiet quitting. *Considering leadership aspects*, Willett et al. (2023) surveyed 1,512 employees working in United States of America. The researchers examined the relationship of leadership communication, two types of workplace respect, and occupational resilience with employee engagement and well-being. It was found that leadership communication adds to a respectful workplace culture in turn positively affecting employee engagement and well-being. Tsemach and Barth's (2023) surveyed 1,100 teachers across 69 Israeli schools to study the relationship between authentic leadership and organizational citizenship behaviour, burnout, and organizational commitment. The researchers noted that "quiet quitting" may be a positive response that helps reduce burnout among overworked teachers.

Conclusion

Although Quiet Quitting is not a new term (as stated by Mark Boldger 2009 and quoted by Formica and Sfodera 2022), however, it has gained popularity recently, particularly after great resignations in the year 2022 (Mark 2023). The foregoing bibliometric analysis identifies the trends, top cited documents, top authors in literature on quiet quitting. The topic is of recent interest for the academicians and researchers as majority of the papers have been published since the year 2022. United States has published maximum papers followed by Greece and India. However, in terms of citations Greece is at the top followed by Italy and United States. Document-wise majority papers have been published in the domain of business and management. Top five cited documents include Formica (2022), Hamouche (2023), Serenko (2024), Boy (2023) and Galanis (2023). Top cited authors are Galanis P, Katsiroumpa A, Moisoglou I, Vraka I and Kaitelidou D. Top five keywords used in the domain are burnout, professional burnout, employee disengagement, healthcare personnel, healthcare workers. Through the lens of keyword analysis, it can be concluded that initially, the researchers focused on the pandemic, healthcare

sector, work environment, engagement, citizenship behaviour, burnout, work-life balance, and well-being. More recently, focus is on the scale development and concepts such as social media, hustle culture, job satisfaction, and turnover intentions in the context of quiet quitting. Further, a deep dive into top papers published in the domain concludes that the researchers have attempted to determine the antecedents of quiet quitting through exploratory research in the hospital and tourism sector. Some of the factors identified are COVID 19, organisational culture, organisational commitment, individual factors, poor management and leadership, employees' needs, values, purpose, work behaviour and conflicts were found as the antecedents of QQ. Few researchers also developed and validated instruments to measure quiet quitting. Researchers also attempted to analyse the impact of sociodemographic variables, job burnout, and job satisfaction on quiet quitting levels, emotional intelligence, leadership aspects and quiet quitting. There are certain areas which have been least or not yet explored in direct context of quitting. It is recommended that the researchers may focus on these grey areas and contribute further to the literature of quiet quitting. These areas are: impact of organisational communication including poor communication, internal communication, loyalty, miscommunication, manipulative communication, ineffective communication, darkside, negative communication on quiet quitting have not been studied so far; impact of role conflict and behaviours such as role ambiguity, stress, arousal, deviant behaviors, role conflict on quiet quitting and; impact of mental and physical well-being of employees like emotional exhaustion, mental energy, work environments, project progress, team dynamics, physical energy, workers are not studied. It is recommended that the future studies may focus on these domains. Further, human resource management policy can affect quiet quitting, thus this relation can also be explored.

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